

The CIRAWA project is working with small-holder farmers in West Africa to improve food nutrition, local livelihoods, and ecosystem health. The project reunites 14 partners from 9 countries who will be developing new agroecological-based practices that build on existing local and scientific knowledge to help create more resilient food supply chains in 8 regions across Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal, and The Gambia. The project aims to demonstrate how working with nature can enhance ecosystem health and biodiversity, while improving local livelihoods and climate resilience using four key agroecological approaches.

1 Purpose

In order to receive regular advice and help with the accomplishment of its objectives, the project formed a Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) that will support the project during its lifetime.

Members of the SAB will provide independent, expert advice to ensure that the project is implemented in the most efficient way to interact with appropriate end-users and reach the final objectives. Members will be invited to have their say and attend all the events planned by the project. The SAB members will have no formal decision power within the project, though the opinions of the distinguished and experienced members will be taken into consideration.

2 Composition

The choice of members invited to join the SAB is based on their expertise and their interest to support the project's main objectives, i.e. to create resilient food systems in West Africa by promoting the use of more agroecological practices among local farmers. In this sense, each SAB member should at least be identified by the each one of the regional contacts as having expertise and experience in one of the following areas:

1. Policy and land planning
2. Gender and related issues
3. Agriculture practices and Agroecological approach
4. Community engagement and sensitization
5. Governance at the local, regional and national level

3 Tasks and activities

The CIRAWA project has a very strong practical component with more than 60 activities and events planned, including technical training activities, field visits to farms, showcase events, policy roundtables, technical symposiums, etc. A principal role of the SAB members would be to advise the CIRAWA country teams on potential agroecological strategies and practices. The SAB members will also be invited to play a more active role, either solicited by the country team, or through their own initiative and send their feedback during the preparation stage of the events and collect their impressions and potential improvements after it.

Other activities could require of the assistance of the SAB members and can include (but is not limited to): Assisting trainings; Collecting data; Campaigning; Administrative and logistical support; Advising on policy briefs or policy changes; Sharing knowledge, among others.

SAB members will be requested and invited to participate in at least two meetings per year, with additional meetings organised based on needs. Country teams can use pre-organised working sessions, for example, the General Assemblies, to invite SAB members for in-person discussions, improving efficiency.

The responsibility for knowledge sharing between countries will stay with the CIRAWA team, and opportunities for inter-country exchanges will be decided through regular reflections.

4 Communication

The official communications between the country SAB and the project will be through the Regional Coordinators, who will ensure the communication is maintained throughout the project duration. The communication with the regional contacts and the members of the SAB will be mainly through email, outside of the recommended semestral meetings. Invitations to participate in events, data-collection/questionnaires, trainings, conferences, or any other activity organized by the project will be shared also via email.

Additionally Regional Coordinators should ensure that all activities are shared with the SAB.

In this sense quarterly emails detailing past and future events, project news/advances, and based on the content, specific dialogues can be fuelled to gather advice or recommendations on key topics. After events, any of several methods can be used to collect feedback from the SAB, including brief discussions after meetings/events, online forms, emails with short questionnaires, or other.

List of regional coordinators

Cape Verde

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